

THE USE OF REMOTE SENSING AND GIS TECHNIQUE FOR APPRAISAL OF SPATIAL GROWTH IN MUBI METROPOLIS, ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA

Nuhu H. Tini, Yohanna Peter and Geoffrey Naphtali
Department of Geography, Adamawa State University, Mubi

ABSTRACT

The spatial growth of urban centre is a contemporary phenomenon in developing countries like Nigeria. Over the years, our cities have experienced spectacular expansion which generates a great concern for urban planners. This study used remote sensing and GIS technology to identify the growth pattern, quantify the spatial growth and explore the causal factors and implications of urban expansion in Mubi metropolis. The research discovered that Mubi experienced population explosion of 41.08% between 1975 and 2006. The built-up area covered 17.3157 km² in 1975 and expanded to 23.8780 km² in 2010. The town grew at the rate of 0.1875 km² and 0.4981% annually. The implications of such growth were found to include imbalance in land use allocation, overcrowding, pollution, loss of natural resources, increased travel distance and cost of transportation. In order to achieve balanced urban growth, we recommended the need to encourage and plan for balanced growth in our cities, introduction of growth management legislation and intensification of site and services by urban planning authorities.

KEYWORDS: Urban growth, GIS, Causes, Implications, Mubi metropolis

INTRODUCTION

The growth of urban areas is a contemporary phenomenon over the entire globe. Okpala (1984) noted that since its independence, Nigeria has experienced not only an enormous urbanization of its population, but also an equally spectacular real physical development and expansion of its existing cities. Urban growth takes place either in radial direction around a well-established city or linearly along the highways. This phenomenon found along road network between urban / semi-urban / rural centres is very much prevalent and persistent in most towns of developing countries like Nigeria. According to Sudhira *et al* (2009) more and more towns and cities are blooming with a change in the land use along the highways and in the immediate vicinity of the city. This dispersed development outside of compact urban and village centres along highways and in rural countryside is defined as sprawl (Theobald, 2001). Such regions are devoid of any infrastructure, since planners are unable to visualise this type of growth patterns.

Urbanisation is a form of metropolitan growth that is a response to often bewildering sets of economic, social, and political forces and to the physical geography of an area. Researches revealed that the causes of the sprawl include - population growth, economy, patterns of infrastructure initiatives like the construction of roads and the provision of infrastructure using public money encouraging development.

Okosun *et al* (2009) revealed that Planning and managing the urban areas has become a difficult task in dealing with issues and problems associated with urban development and growth. Besides, the loss of urban greenery, increase in water and air pollution, erosion, flooding, haze, and unpleasant odour occur due to improper physical planning. Therefore, effective urban planning and management practice is imperative in order to forestall further unplanned urban growth in the country.

According to Sudhira *et al* (2009), the investigation of spatial patterns of town growth is very crucial and analysing the sprawl over a period of time will help in understanding the nature and growth of this phenomenon. Prior visualising of the trends and patterns of growth enable the planning machineries to plan for appropriate basic infrastructure facilities (water, electricity, sanitation, etc.). Study of the type, extent and nature of sprawl taking place in a place and the drivers responsible for the growth would help developers and town planners to project growth patterns and facilitate various infrastructure facilities. In this research, an attempt was made to identify the growth pattern of Mubi metropolis, quantify spatial

growth, explore the causal factors and estimate the rate of change in built-up area over a period of 35 years with the help of spatial and statistical data using GIS.

The Study Area

Mubi is the second largest town in Adamawa state which covers an area of about 600 Sq Km. The town lies about 260 Km north of Yola the state capital. Mubi metropolitan area is situated between Latitude 10 ° 05' N/ 10 ° 30' N and Longitude 13 °10' E/ 13 °30'E. The town is centrally located on the border line between Mubi-North L.G.A and Mubi-South L.G.A. (Figure 1)

Mubi town originated as a farmstead founded by Fali and Gude peasants who settled to cultivate the fertile plains of River Yadzeram. The influx of Fulani cattle rears in the 18th century and merchants in the 19th century increased the native peasant population (Tini, 2001). This resulted to the emergence of several hamlets in the vicinity. Mubi Township came into existence on 1st April 1936 by amalgamating the village units of Lokuwa, Wuro Gude, Kolere, Shuware and the hamlets of Wuro Alkali, Wuro Bulude, Wuro Hamsobe and Wuro Yombe. These settlements were merged to form a central administrative setup called Jimilla.

The growth of Mubi town is traced to the agricultural, administrative, and commercial functions it performs. By 1902, Mubi was a German base from where the neighbouring tribes (i.e Fali, Gude, Kilba, Higgi, Margi and Njanyi) of the region were subjugated. On 1st April 1960, Mubi was made Native Authority headquarters. The same year, July 1960, the town became provincial headquarters of the defunct Sardauna province. In 1967, Mubi was made L.G.A headquarters while in 1996, the town was splinted into Mubi-North and Mubi-South Local Government Areas. Currently, the town is the seat of Mubi Emirate Council and the headquarters of Adamawa-North Senatorial District.

Mubi is geographically well placed and functions not only as center of commerce in the region but also extends its sphere of influence to countries such as Cameroun, Central Africa Republic and Chad. Numerous banks, filling stations and hotels exist in the town to support the commercial activities. Another factor that led to growth of the town is rural-urban migration experienced from the surrounding villages. More over the town has become center of learning with numerous tertiary and secondary institutions established in the metropolis.

The use of GIS and Remote Sensing Techniques for analysis of urban growth

GIS and remote sensing are land related technologies which have become very useful in the formulation and implementation of the land related component of the sustainable development strategy. GIS can address the challenges of proffering an acceptable solution for smart growth of cities. For example, with a visual GIS-based model, older suburbs can be assisted in assessing their redevelopment plans and the implications of their land-use development on quality of life within the communities (Okosun *et al.*, 2009).The spatial patterns of urban sprawl over different time periods, can be systematically mapped, monitored and accurately assessed from satellite data (remotely sensed data) along with conventional ground data (Lata *et al.*,2001).

Sudhira *et al* (2009) envisaged that mapping urban sprawl provides a “picture” of where this type of growth is occurring, helps to identify the environmental and natural resources threatened by such sprawls, and to suggest the likely future directions and patterns of sprawling growth.

The remote sensing satellite with high-resolution sensors and wide coverage capabilities provides data with better resolution and coverage to meet the growing applications needs. Image processing techniques are also quite effective in identifying the urban growth pattern from the spatial and temporal data captured by the remote sensing techniques. The above mentioned techniques aid in delineating specific growth patterns of sprawl which could be linear or radial or both. The physical expressions and patterns of sprawl on landscapes can as well be detected, mapped, and analyzed using remote sensing and geographical information system (GIS) (Barnes *et al.*, 2001).

Sudhira *et al* (2009) noted that in recent years, considerable interest has been focused on the use of GIS as a decision support system. The use of GIS as a direct extension of the human decision making process—most particularly in the context of resource allocation decisions is indeed a great challenge and an important milestone. According to Okosun *et al* (2009), the advent of (GIS) has created a large field of opportunity for development of new approaches to computer processing of geographically referenced data, which add a new dimension to the management, analysis and presentation of large volumes of information required in decision-making process. The use of GIS has enhanced the rationality of the decision making process by improving data and accessibility and as a consequence leads to better decision.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data collection

The data collection for this research was carried out in two phases. This involved primary data collection and secondary data collection methods. The primary data involved Conventional map, satellite image and demographic details as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Baseline Data

S/N	Data Type	Data Source	Date	Other characteristics
1	Mubi Metropolitan map	Federal Ministry of Survey, Lagos	1975	Scale of 1:30,000
2	Satellite image of Mubi Metropolitan	QuickBird	2005	Multispectral Resolution (2.4m), Band: Multispectral Panchromatic, Format: Geo TIFF
3	Demographic data	National Population Commission	1952-2006	

Figure 1. Conventional Map of the Study

Figure 2 Satellite image of the Study Area

Materials

A Laptop Computer HP 530, HP colour printer, hand held GPS (Garmin 72) and Genx A4 Scanner were the main hardware used for this study. GIS software packages were also used. ILWIS 3.1 Academics was used for geo-referencing and Idrisi for digitization, map overlay, calculation of area and map analysis. Other non-GIS Software packages used include CorelDraw 12 for map scanning and map export to ILWIS, Microsoft word 2003 for word processing.

Methodology

The researchers took the GPS reading of two round-abouts (police round-about and Lokuwa round- about) and two road junctions (Maiha road junction and Gella road junction) for the purpose of geo-referencing the Quick Bird satellite imagery.

In order to geo-reference the satellite image, four identifiable points on the image were visited. Two out of the four points were round-about (police round-about and Lokuwa round- about) while the other two points were road junctions (Maiha road junction and Gella road junction). In each of these points, GPS was turned on and coordinates were observed and recorded. The coordinates of the four points picked were 10° 15 52.89"N, 13° 16' 10.51"E (police round-about) 10° 16' 23.86"N, 13° 16' 40.48"E (Lokuwa round-about) 10° 16' 08.53"N, 13° 15' 10.71"E (Maiha road junction) and 10° 15' 48.78"N, 13° 16' 30.22"E (Gella road junction). These coordinates were transformed to Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) through the transform module of ILWIS 3.1 to create the geo-reference points. Geo-referencing ensures that coordinates of pixels in the image correspond to the true coordinates of the points they depict on the ground. The transformation gave the minimum "X" and "Y" values 306150.24, 1139028.81 respectively and also 314191.88, 1139332.43 as maximum "X" and "Y" respectively. The four points picked with GPS were identified on the satellite image and were used as tie points. The referenced satellite image was then resampled and some points were again picked and compared with the same points on the referenced map to ascertain that the coordinates on the ground corresponds to the coordinates on the map, this is called *ground truthing*. The image was then exported to Idrisi 32 for digitizing.

The conventional map of Mubi was scanned using the Genx scanner through CorelDraw 12 and imported to Ilwis environment via Tagged Image File Format (TIFF) where the map was also geo-referenced using the four tie points. The referenced map was then resampled using the minimum and maximum coordinates of the resampled satellite imagery, so that the two maps (conventional map and satellite imagery) can have the same rows and columns to enable them overlay correctly. They were then exported to Idrisi environment for digitizing. The access roads, minor roads, major roads, footpaths and the border were digitized as line features. The built-up areas of 1975 and 2010 were digitized as polygon.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research discovered that Mubi metropolis has been experiencing explosive population growth since 1970s. Table 2 shows the rate at which Mubi has undergone population increase since 1952.

Table 2. Population growth of Mubi Metropolis

Year	Population	Percentage of Growth	Reference
1952	11,782	1.87%	Mabogunje, 1978
1962	28,090	4.44%	Uyanga, 1982
1974	44,000	6.95%	Max Lock Group, 1976
1991	128,900	20.35%	National Population Census(NPC), 1991
2000	160,200	25.31%	NPC Projection, 2000
2006	260,009	41.08%	NPC, 2006

This rapid population growth revealed in table 2 results to increased housing demand. There by instigating development of more structures and patterns of infrastructures initiatives like road construction, eventually leading to spatial expansion of the study area.

The built-up area of Mubi metropolis in 1975 and 2010 were separately digitized as shown in Figures 4 and 5 respectively. The percentage of built up area of 1975 and 2010 were calculated using the area subroutine of GIS analysis module of the Idirisi software and the result is presented on Table 3.

Table 3. Build- up Area for 1975 and 2010

S/N	Build-up Area	Area in Km ²	Percentage
1	1975	17.3157	42.03%
2	2010	23.8780	57.97%
	TOTAL	41.1937	100

The Table 3 reveals that between 1975 and 2010; a period of 35 years, Mubi metropolis grew at the rate of 0.1875 Km² and 0.4981% annually. Okosun *et al* (2009) highlighted that the implication of such rapid urban growth are imbalance in land use allocation, overcrowding, pollution and loss of natural resources. Other implications of urban growth include increased travel distance and cost of transportation and urban delinquency.

The 1975 and 2010 maps were overlaid (Figure 5). Query modules were used to find the value of areas with same colour. All areas with deep blue colour represents the built up areas of 1975 while all areas with sky blue colour represents built up areas of 2010. Some of the new wards which developed after 1975 include Saminaka, Araham-Kunu, Gerewol, unguwan Kara, Gizga-Lamurde, Va'atita, Gi'ipalma, Barama, Sabon-Gari, Gi'ima, Shagari-Lowcost and Dazala. The growth pattern of Mubi metropolis which is in radial direction around the city center is quit glaring in Figure 5.

Figure 3. Build-up Area, 1975

RECOMMENDATIONS

There is a need to encourage and plan for balanced growth in our cities. This is to be achieved by targeting some areas for growth and environmental protection.

Okosun *et al* (2009) recommend that growth management legislations need to be introduced at various levels of governments to identify lands with high natural resource, economic and environmental value and protect them from development.

Site and services should also be intensified by urban planning authorities in which public services such as water and sewer lines, roads and schools be in place before new development is approved. Governments should as well make decisions in accordance with comprehensive plans that are consistent with plans for adjoining areas in Mubi metropolis.

Urban planning authorities need to explore the use of remote sensing and GIS for evaluation of urban growth. A computer-generated data base and information system in GIS environment enhances continuous data collection, analysis, interpretation and updating data. This would provide support to planners in development of planning.

According to Verma *et al* (2008), satellite remote sensing with repetitive and synoptic viewing capabilities, as well as multispectral capabilities, is a powerful tool for mapping and monitoring the ecological changes in the urban core and in the peripheral land-use planning. The use of remote sensing needs to be introduced for monitoring the activities of developers. This will help in reducing unplanned urban sprawls and the associated loss of natural surrounding and biodiversity.

REFERENCES

- Barnes, K. B., Morgan III J. M., Roberge M C., and Lowe S, (2001). “*Sprawl development: Its patterns, consequences, and measurement*”, Towson University. Available online:
http://chesapeake.towson.edu/landscape/urbansprawl/download/Sprawl_white_paper.pdf
- Lata, K. M., Sankar Rao C. H., Krishna Prasad V., Badrinath K. V. S., Raghavaswamy, (2001). “Measuring urban sprawl: a case study of Hyderabad”, *GIS development, Vol. 5 (12)*.
- Mabogunje, A. L., (1978) *Urbanization in Nigeria*. New York Africana Publishing Corporation, P. 28.
- Max Lock Group (1976) *Mubi Town Master Plan*. Federal Ministry of Works, Lagos
- National Population Census (1991)*. Government Official Gazette.
- National Population Commission Projection (2000)*.
- National and State Provisional Total Census (2006)*. www.nigerianstat.gov.ng Retrieved on 6th june, 2009.
- Okosun , A. E. et al (2009) Urban Growth Management of Nigerian Cities: A GIS Approach. In *Journal of Environmental Management and Safety (JEMS)* Journal homepage: www.cepajournal.com
- Okpala, D. C. I. (1984) Urban planning and the control of urban physical growth in Nigeria: *A critique of public impact and private roles. Habitat Intl. Vol. 8 No. 2. PP 73-94*
- Sudhira, H. S., (2009) *Urban sprawl pattern recognition and modeling using GIS*. Energy and Wetland Research Group, Centre for Ecological Sciences, Indian. Institute of Science, Bangalore – 560 012, India
- Theobald, D. M., 2001, “Quantifying urban and rural sprawl using the sprawl index”, *Paper presented at the annual conference of the Association of American Geographers in New York, on March 2nd, 2001.*

Nuhu H. Tini *et al.*,: Continental J. Environmental Design and Management 1 (1): 1 - 8, 2011

Tini, N. H. (2001) *An appraisal of the effectiveness of development control in Mubi town, Adamawa State.* Unpublished M. Sc. Thesis, Department Geography and planning, University of Jos, Nigeria

Uyanga, J. (1982) *Towards a Nigerian National Urban Policy.* Ibadan, University Press, P. 211.

Verma, R. K. (2008) Application of Remote Sensing and GIS technique for efficient Urban planning in India. *GIS@development.net/application/urban.*

Received for Publication: 02/01/2011

Accepted for Publication: 15/02/2011

Corresponding Author

Yohanna Peter

Department of Geography, Adamawa State University, Mubi

Email: nuhutini@gmail.com